

IMPROVING COMPARATIVE ADVANTAGE AND BUSINESS PERFORMANCE THROUGH RIGHT COLLABORATION STRATEGY

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Abstract:

Purpose: This study aims to examine how to optimally utilize company resources thru the development and implementation of appropriate collaboration strategies that will increase comparative advantage and business performance. Namely studying the influence of company resources on collaboration strategies and company performance and the influence of company resources on company performance through collaboration strategies.

Research Design: This study uses a quantitative research approach. Observations were made in a cross-section/one-shot, in 2022. The population of this study was the ISP industry in Indonesia, which amounted to 474 companies, and the unit of observation was the management. Samples were taken from as many as 240 respondents. Testing the causality hypothesis in this study used Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). **Results:** Company resources play a significant role in developing and implementing collaboration strategy, company resources don't have a significant direct effect on business performance. While for the indirect relationship between company resources with business performance thru collaboration strategy, research shows significant results. **Findings:** Efforts to improve business performance can be done by developing and implementing the right collaboration strategies through optimal use of company resources to increase the comparative advantage.

Key-Words: Company Resources, Collaboration Strategy, Business Performance, Comparative Advantage, Internet Service Provider.

1. INTRODUCTION

Based on research conducted by the Indonesian Internet Providers Association (APJII) in the year of, the growth in the number of Internet users in Indonesia is 9 times greater than the population growth in Indonesia, this is inseparable from the main role of ISPs (internet service providers) in Indonesia, which currently based on APJII data are 474 providers. In addition to facing competition with the 474 local ISPs, ISPs also face competition with the presence of Global ISPs that already have licenses to operate in Indonesia, such as Starlink. According to Iman Sanjaya (2014), ISP is a company or entity that provides internet connection services and other related services. ISPs have a basic function as an internet connection service provider and other services, such as protection from the spread of viruses by implementing an antivirus system for its users.

Because of hyper-competition, continuously dropping internet rates, and government regulations that do not support the ISP industry, it's made the profitability growth of ISP companies tend to decline. This situation is exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic which has caused a further decline in ISP income. So, it is interesting to examine why the business

performance of ISP companies in Indonesia is not optimal while the growth of internet users grows 9x the population growth.

Such conditions indicate problems in the business performance of ISP companies in Indonesia. According to Krause (2005) at Ghalem et al. (2016), performance refers to the level of achievement of goals or possible achievements that may be related to important characteristics of the organization for the relevant stakeholders.

The majority of ISPs in Indonesia are small category companies that are only able to provide basic internet connection services with relatively lagging technology and infrastructure compared to Global ISPs, only operate in one or two cities, and have difficulty developing their service coverage areas, difficulty developing new products/services to meet customer demands and technological trends such as; digital connectivity value-added service (bandwidth on demand, network security, etc), digital platform (IoT, Big Data, Payment, etc), Digital Services (Video, Game, Metaverse, etc), this is due to limited human resources capabilities, limited capital for investment and the limited number of experts and technological capabilities possessed by ISPs. This situation requires ISP companies to have superior resources to have a comparative advantage and win the competition. Companies are required to be able to utilize their resources as a comparative advantage to improve performance, as is the case with the RBV concept, companies must understand the relationship between resources, capabilities, competitive advantage, and profitability to maintain long-term competitiveness (Barney, 1991). Thompson et al. (2020), divide company resources into two main categories, namely: tangible resources and intangible resources.

The relationship between company resources and business performance shown from previous research shows inconsistent results (research gap). Hafeez et al. (2012), Oladele and Omotayo (2014), Bagheri et al. (2013), Karami et al. (2015), and Ye (2015) stated that company resources had a significant effect on business performance, while Hussain and Waheed (2019) stated that company resources had no significant effect on business performance. Therefore, this research intends to fill the research gap by including the collaboration strategy variable as a mediation, on the relationship between company resources with company performance. Besides also examines the influence of company resources on business performance.

Based on information from APJII, due to high customer demands, Covid-19 pandemic conditions, hyper-competition, very fast technological developments, and government regulations that do not support the ISP industry, these things cause ISP companies to collaborate with banks to get relief from loan interest payments. , collaboration with customers to find out and fulfill what customers want, collaboration with the government to issue policies that support the ISP industry such as tax breaks, deferral of payment of universal service obligation fees, and partnerships with hardware and software suppliers to get the right technology, reduce costs, and reduce investment costs through a vendor financing cooperation scheme. Through collaboration, companies are expected to be able to have "Strategic Resources" that will have a long-term competitive advantage over other companies that do not have them, This was obtained from VRI (valuable, rare, inimitable) resources (Barney, 1991). So, the collaboration strategy is suspected as a mediation between company resources with

business performance, which is expected to improve business performance. This assumption is strengthened by the results of previous studies that show the mediating role of collaboration strategy on the relationship between company resources with business performance, namely research from Roja and Nastase (2013), and Wu et al. (2011).

The need to collaborate in the ISP industry is in line with the trend of coopetition (collaboration & competition) (Mariani & Belitski (2022), Ritala (2012), Ritala & Hurmelinna-Laukkanen (2013), Estrada et al. (2016); Quintana-García & BenavidesVelasco (2004)) found that coopetition positively affects innovation for improving performance because it can give birth to innovations, new knowledge, new skills, new capabilities, and technological diversity by accessing each other's resources and capabilities from collaborative activities. Coopetition in essence is the occurrence of cooperation and competition between industry players which can be carried out in various configurations that support business activities together, Sammut-Bonnici (2015).

Therefore, this study aims to examine how to optimally utilize company resources through the adoption of appropriate collaboration strategies that will increase comparative advantage and business performance. So the company's limited resources can be overcome by implementing the right collaboration strategy to improve business performance and increase its comparative advantage.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following explanation of variables, dimensions, and indicators utilized in this study is based on the findings of earlier research:

The concept of business performance is the output or result of the implementation of all activities related to business activities, which is concluded from the opinion; of Best (2014), that company performance is the result of all activities related to business activities, with indicators of market share growth, sales, and profitability. Wheelen and Hunger (2018) state that performance is the result of activities measured in terms of EBITDA margin, market share, or cost reduction. David (2013) evaluates business performance using ratios, namely: Return on Investment (ROI), Return on Equity (ROE), Ebitda Margin, Market Share, and Debt to Equity, Earnings per share, Sales growth, and Asset growth. Tifow & Sayilir (2015) use Return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA), and earnings per share (EPS), as indicators of firm success. ROA is also used by Hahn and Powers (2013) to evaluate business success. Similar to Al-Tamimi (2010), who gauges business success using ROA and ROE. In their study on digital technology, digital capabilities, and organizational performance.

Collaboration Strategy is planned collaborative activity for mutual benefit, which involves all relevant stakeholders including horizontal stakeholders, vertical stakeholders, and complementary stakeholders, in developing business activities to create sustainable corporate performance, which is the cohesion of the collaboration concept (Gray, 1989; Wood & Gray, 1991; Gray, 2000, Barrat, 2004, Gutierrez et al. 2016) with the concept of Collaborative Advantage through shared meta-strategies (Huxham & MacDonald, 1992). Meanwhile,

Björnfot et al. (2011) said Supply chain collaboration is most often realized horizontally or vertically in the supply chain. Gutierrez et al. (2016) said the partnership strategy is part of a business strategy that includes partnerships with suppliers, complementary, customers, and competitors. Cravens and Piercy (2013) explain that organizational relationship is a collaborative effort with various stakeholders carried out through vertical relationships, namely with suppliers and customers as well as horizontal relationships, namely lateral partnerships and internal partnerships. Simatupang and Sridharan (2002), in Barratt (2004), collaboration is divided into two categories; first vertical collaboration: which can include collaboration with customers, internal (cross-functional), and suppliers; and second, horizontal collaboration: which can include collaboration with competitors, internally and with other organizations.

The concept of company resources used in this study refers to the opinion of Thompson et al. (2014) which states that the company's resources and capabilities are the basic building blocks of the company's competitive strategy. Resources are productive inputs or competitive assets owned and controlled by the company. Resources are divided into two main categories, namely: tangible resources and intangible resources. Tangible assets are most easily identifiable and can be found on a company's balance sheet, including production facilities, raw materials, and financial resources (Pearce & Robinson, 2015).

2.1 Variable dimensions

The business performance variable in this study was measured using 5 indicators referred to by Best (2014), Wheelen & Hunger (2018), Tifow & Sayilir (2015), and David (201): ROA, EBITDA margin, ROIC, asset growth, and market share control.

The collaboration strategy variable in this study was measured by dimensions referred to by Cravens and Piercy (2013), Gutierrez et al. (2016), Simatupang and Sridharan (2002), Barratt (2004), and Björnfot et al. (2011), so that the constructs of collaboration strategy dimensions are obtained which include: partnerships with suppliers, partnerships with customers, partnerships with laterals, internal partnerships, and partnerships with complementary.

According to Thompson et al. (2020), Hafeez et al. (2012), and Amit & Schoemaker (2016), the company resource variables in this research were assessed along two dimensions: tangible and intangible resources.

2.2 Research Model Framework

As explained in the introduction that this study aims to examine the effect of company resources on collaboration strategy and business performance, as well as the effect of company resources on business performance through collaboration strategy, based on the study literature and previous research that produced the variables, dimensions, and indicators of this study, then the framework of this research model is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: research model framework

2.3 Hypothesis

The influence of company Resources on collaboration strategy

According to Gavrilă-Păven and Muntean (2011) said efforts to identify and respond to market changes in search of flexibility and innovative ways to develop company activities are carried out through partnerships. Similar findings were found in the research results of Roja and Nastase (2013) that collaborative competitive advantage is the result of a strategy that focuses on collaboration and organizational capabilities in utilizing the organization's distinctive and unique capabilities, especially to access complementary resources in collaboration with other organizations.

Based on the findings of these studies, the first hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H1: company resources have a significant effect on the collaboration strategy.

The influence of company resources on business performance

Oladele and Omotayo (2014) stated that there was a strong positive relationship between the e-HRM variable and company organizational performance. Karami et al. (2015) found that HR practices had a positive effect on bank performance, while Bagheri et al. (2013) found that manager competence had an effect on business performance, and manager competency indicators had a significant relationship with business performance. Meanwhile, Hussain and Waheed (2019) found that the capital resources used had an insignificant and mixed effect on the operating performance and financial performance of the company. Intellectual capital also affects stock market performance, but not significantly. Izadi et al. (2020) found that there were three components emotional and intellectual assets (knowledge and competence, digital technology, and reputation) that affect business performance. Yasa et al. (2019) show that digital capabilities have a significant influence on business performance.

Based on the findings of these studies, the third hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H2: company resources have a significant effect on business performance.

The influence of collaboration strategy on business performance

Entrepreneurship, marketing capabilities, relational capital, and empowerment have a good and important effect on innovation capability and performance (Sulistyo and Siyamtinah, 2016). Collaboration has a positive effect on business transformation (Steiber and Alange, 2019). Variables related to buyer involvement with international markets affect company performance (Jajja et al., 2016).

Based on the findings of these studies, the fifth hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H3: collaboration strategy affects business performance

The influence of company resources on business performance through collaboration strategy

Roja and Nastase (2013) describe that an organization's ability to integrate and collaborate within a network or to develop partnerships increases the opportunity to leverage its capabilities and benefit from the synergies generated through collaboration. According to the research of Wu et al. (2011), companies should emphasize evaluating the capabilities of their suppliers and integrating resources, particularly innovation and quality, to enhance collaboration to build core competencies of the supply chain through strategic alliances and technical cooperation all of which can help companies to achieve competitive advantage. Higher and helps the growth of the company's constant performance.

Based on the findings of these studies, the seventh hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H4: collaboration strategy mediates the influence of company resources on business performance.

3 METHODS

This study uses a quantitative research approach. Observations were carried out in a cross-section/one shot, in 2022. The population of this study was the ISP company industry, and the unit of observation was the management. Sampling used stratified random sampling, in which population elements were grouped at certain levels to take samples evenly throughout the group so that the sample represented the character of all heterogeneous population elements.

The survey was conducted by selecting a sample of the population, namely licensed ISP companies operating in Indonesia and being members of APJII (Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association) totaling around 474. ISPs are grouped based on the size of each company based on the number of customers and branch cities which are divided into 3 groups, namely: small, medium, and large. Samples were taken from as many as 240 respondents. Sampling from each classification is done randomly based on a list of population members. The measurement scale in this study uses an ordinal scale using the Likert method which produces ordinal data. The ordinal measurement scale is a scale where the data shows a certain order or order (Ferdinand, 2014). Testing the causality hypothesis in this study used Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

4 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Goodness of Fit

Structural equation modeling is an ideal data analytical tool for testing complex relationships among many analytical variables. To test the extent to which a hypothesized model provides an appropriate characterization of the collective relationships among its variables, researchers must assess the “fit” between the model and the sample’s data. A guideline for assessing if a theory-based model fits empirical data or if the resulting model describes actual conditions. Structural Equation Model (SEM) as a statistical test can explain the strength of a model with several index criteria to assess the suitability of the model.

The following Table.1 are the results of the Goodness of fit of this study, Chi-Square = 282, 18, and the Chi-Square p-value = 0.60181 > 0.05. Therefore, according to the Chi-Square index, the suitability of this research model is fit (Hair et al., 2010). The RMSEA is less than 0.05. Besides that, Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) = 0.92 > 0.80, likewise AGFI = 0, 90 > 0, 8. So, it can be concluded that the research model is in an empirical condition.

Table 1: Goodness of Fit

No.	Ukuran Derajat Kecocokan	Nilai	Tingkat kecocokan yang bisa diterima	Keterangan
1	Absolut Fit Test			
	Chi Square	282.18	P -value >0,05	fit
	Normed Chi Square (x2/df)	P -value = 0.60181		
	Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	0,92	>0,80	fit
	Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	0,000	RMSEA ≤ 0,08 (good fit) RMSEA < 0,05 (close-fit)	fit
2	Incremental Fit Measures			
	Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	0,90	AGFI > 0,8	Fit
	Normed Fit Index (NFI)	0.93	NFI > 0.90	Fit
	Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.98	CFI > 0.90	Fit
3	Parsimonius Fit Measures			
	Parsimonious Normed Fit Index (PNFI)	0.93	PNFI > 0.90	fit
	Parsimonious GFI (PGFI)	0.90	PGFI > 0.90	fit

Source: Output LISREL 8.7

4.2 Measurement Model

After the model is declared fit, the next process is to see indicators in a construct. This process is called the construct validity test (latent variable) which is carried out through the convergent validity test, which is an indicator that composes data the construct has a high loading factor

with that construct Internal reliability and composite reliability commonly employed to evaluate construct reliability. And convergent validity was achieved through Average Variance Extracted and factor loadings with an expected value >0.50.

Figure 2: Estimate Model Results

Table 2: Research Measurement

Variable	Dimension-Indikator	Loading Factor	t value	Prob.	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Composite Reliability
Company Resources	Tangible Resources	0,91	7,33	0,000	0,632	0,873
	Representative Office building facilities	0,78	-	-		
	sufficient Capital	0,79	8,10	0,000		
	adequate human resources	0,81	8,32	0,000		
	Intangible Resources	0,90	7,41	0,000	0,644	0,900
	build and maintain company's reputation	0,78	-	-		
	provide superior customer service	0,81	8,64	0,000		
	mastery on IT technology	0,81	8,64	0,000		
	supported organizational culture	0,84	9,01	0,000		

	develops internal business processes	0,77	8,12	0,000		
Collaboration Strategy	Suppliers	0,87	7,04	0,000	0,624	0,769
	software suppliers	0,78	-	-		
	hardware suppliers	0,80	7,53	0,000		
	Customers	0,94	7,45	0,000	0,583	0,807
	develops customer loyalty	0,76	-	-		
	develops customer database	0,78	7,76	0,000		
	provides easy and fast customer service	0,75	7,41	0,000		
	Lateral	0,89	7,16	0,000	0,598	0,817
	partnership with government	0,76	-	-		
	partnership with business associations	0,78	7,66	0,000		
	partnership with competitors	0,78	7,63	0,000		
	Internal	0,92	7,74	0,000	0,616	0,763
	Cross-functional coordination within the company is always done well	0,80	-	-		
	Communication within the company is always carried out effectively	0,77	7,84	0,000		
	Complementor	0,92	7,32	0,000	0,593	0,744
	partnership with banks	0,77	-	-		
	Partnership with educational institutions	0,77	7,40	0,000		
Business Performance	ROA	0,76	-	-	0,626	0,833
	Ebitda Margin	0,75	7,56	0,000		
	ROIC	0,84	8,57	0,000		
	Asset growth	0,78	7,90	0,000		
	Market share control	0,79	7,98	0,000		

In figure 1 and table 2 it is known that the loading factor is > 0.50 , and the t value of the loading factor is higher than the t-table at a significance of 5%, according to Chin (2000) dimensions and indicators are valid in measuring latent variables. Composite Reliability and Alpha Cronbach are used to see the level of reliability of indicators and dimensions in measuring research variables. Cronbach's Alpha value is greater than 0.70 (Nunnally, 1994), composite reliability $> 0,7$, and AVE $> 0,5$, then the dimensions and indicators are declared valid and reliable in measuring the research variables.

4.3 Hypothesis Testing

The following are the results of hypothesis testing:

Table 3: Hypothesis Testing

No	Structural Model	Coefficient Estimated	t value	R2	P Value	Conclusion
1	Company Resources → Collaboration Strategy	0,62	4,91	0,384	0,000	Significant
3	Company Resources → Business Performance	0,21	1,71	0,044	0,089	Not Significant
5	Collaboration Strategy → Business Performance	0,56	4,13	0,314	0,000	Significant
7	Company resources → Collaboration Strategy → Business Performance	0,347	3,197	0,120	0,002	Significant

Based on the results of hypothesis testing revealed in table 3, it was found that:

- Company Resources have significant direct effect on Collaboration Strategy with t-value >1.98 (Prob < 0.05). Company resources have the dominant influence on Collaboration Strategy with R2 = 0,384
- Company Resources have no significant direct effect on Business Performance with a t-value <1.98 (Prob >0, 05).
- Collaboration Strategy has a significant direct effect on Business Performance with a t-value >1.98 (Prob < 0.05). Collaboration strategy has the dominant influence on Business Performance with R2=0,314
- Company Resources have significant indirect effect on Business performance through Collaboration Strategy, and Company resources have the dominant influence on Business performance through Collaboration Strategy with R2=0.196

In terms of the relationship between company resources with collaboration strategy, this finding supports the research results of Roja and Nastase (2013) which describe the significant role of company resources in collaboration strategy. For the relationship between collaboration strategies with business performance, this finding supports the result of Sulisty and Siyamtinah (2016), Steiber and Alange (2019), and Jajja et al. (2016) that said collaboration strategy has a significant influence on business performance. But these findings didn't support previous research that stated there is a significant direct effect of company resources on business performance (Hafeez et al. (2012), Oladele and Omotayo (2014), Bagheri et al. (2013), Karami et al. (2015), and Ye (2015)) but support the finding from Hussain and Waheed (2019), stated that company resources had no significant effect on business performance.

For the Indirect effect of company resources on business performance through collaboration strategy, the finding supports the research results of Roja and Nastase (2013), and Wu et al. (2011).

Based on research results, the company's resources have been proven to affect the business performance of ISP companies only with an indirect effect thru collaboration strategy. The indirect effect of company resources on business performance thru collaboration strategy is very dominant with $R^2=0,196$. Table 2 shows that tangible resources have a little bit bigger loading factor (0, 91) than intangible resources (0, 90). The aspects of tangibles resources are adequate human resources, facilities, sufficient capital, and representative office building. And for the aspects of intangible resources are supportive organizational culture, providing superior customer service, mastery of IT technology, building and maintaining a good company reputation, and developing internal business processes.

Empirically, to overcome various limitations on the company's resources, the ISP Company must make optimal use of its resources to conduct strategic collaboration with suppliers, customers, lateral, internal, and complementary, to obtain other resources and other capabilities needed by the company to improve business performance.

The collaboration strategy has a significant direct effect on business performance, thus the collaborative strategy also has a mediating effect on the indirect relationship between the business environment and business performance. Table 2 shows that partnership with the customer has the higher loading factor (0, 94) and followed by partnership with complementary, internal partnership, partnership with lateral, and partnership with suppliers.

5 CONCLUSION

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that in the ISP industry In Indonesia, company resources play a significant role in developing collaboration strategy. Company Resources don't have a significant direct effect on business performance and have a significant indirect effect on business performance thru collaboration strategy.

The findings of this study are novel and very interesting to be applied because it provides theoretical and managerial implications that can be directly applied to improve the company's business performance. Theoretical implications of this study, namely a model for improving business performance thru the development and implementation of the right collaboration strategy by optimally utilizing the company's resources, this model also increases the company's comparative advantage compared to the competitors. By utilizing company resources optimally for implementing and developing strategic collaboration, ISP company will get another resource, innovation results, technological capabilities, and other strategic capabilities that are needed to improve company performance from partners. Company resources are a strategic component of the company as a comparative advantage that cloud be used to increase partner interest and the bargaining power in establishing partnerships to get the most optimum partnership results to improve business performance and will make the company a comparative advantage compared to the competitors. Meanwhile, the managerial implications of this study are the improvement of ISP company business performance could be done by developing and implementing the right strategic collaboration by utilizing company resources optimally. Until now to improve business performance, ISP companies must immediately develop all company resources and capabilities independently, which of course

will increase the required costs and will further erode the profits of ISP companies which are currently declining. Next, with the implementation of the right collaboration strategy by utilizing the company's resources optimally, ISP companies could focus only on developing key resources, capabilities, and additional innovations that are needed outside of the partnership result, it will provide huge cost savings and improve the profitability of ISP Company. The results of this study also provide managerial implications for the government, namely what is needed to develop the ISP industry in Indonesia and used it for reviewing various ISP industry regulations and improving support needed from ISP Industry in Indonesia to provide the best service.

To improve business performance through the development and implementation of appropriate collaborative strategies by optimally utilizing company resources, ISP companies must take the following operational steps:

- a. Prioritizing the achievement of performance indicators, namely by first ensuring that the ROIC (return on invested capital) target is achieved because the ISP industry is a capital-intensive industry in deploying its service infrastructure, this capital is generally obtained from bank loans, so ISPs must ensure they can repay the loan, then, the achievement of market share control indicators through asset growth while still ensuring the level of ROA (return on assets) and the company's EBITDA margin.
- b. The development and implementation of the right collaboration strategy begin with prioritizing partnerships with customers because a good partnership with customers will allow companies to know early what customers want and need for ISP company products and services, partnerships with customers are carried out through customer database development, customer royalties and provide fast and easy customer service. Then proceed with partnerships with complementors, namely partnerships with banking and partnerships with educational institutions that will provide support for financial resources and technological resources as well as innovation resources. Internal partnerships are carried out through cross-functional coordination within the company which is always carried out properly and communication within the company is always carried out effectively. Lateral partnerships are carried out to overcome the problems of competition, government regulation, and access to abundant resources in competitors, thru a partnership with business associations, partnerships with competitors, and partnerships with the government. Partnerships with suppliers are carried out through partnerships with hardware suppliers first because the largest investment to develop internet network infrastructure is in hardware then partnerships with software suppliers, one form of partnership with suppliers is called "vendor financing" which can overcome the limited investment capability of ISP companies due to limited capital owned.
- c. In utilizing company resources optimally, the ISP company needs to utilize tangible resources first, in the form of adequate human resources, complete facilities, capital adequacy, and representative offices, then intangible resources, in the form of a supportive organizational culture, mastery of IT technology, superior customer service, company reputation, and internal business processes.

It would be interesting to continue this research by adding digital innovation as a second mediating variable to the model of this research, adding digital innovation as a second mediating variable in this model besides collaboration strategy is based on the Resource Based View (RBV) theory (Barney, 1991) says that to have a competitive advantage, a company must have the capability to innovate using its available resources and the company can have strategic resources through collaboration.

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